

The role of using innovative pedagogical technologies in science education

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Abstract

The article shows that great attention is being paid to the education system in our country, that a great future cannot be achieved without reforming the education system, that this process imposes a great responsibility on pedagogues, because the education received at school, academic lyceum, vocational college, and higher educational institutions is of great importance in the fate of every person. analyzed.

Key words: education, responsibility, pedagogue, pedagogy, future.

As we all know, today a lot of attention is paid to the education system in our country. After all, a great future cannot be achieved without reforming the education system. Of course, this process imposes a great responsibility on us pedagogues. After all, the education he received at school, academic lyceum, vocational college and higher educational institutions is important in the fate of every person. The quality of education in educational institutions depends primarily on teachers and trainers. Of course, there are many teachers among us who constantly work on themselves and try to teach on the basis of new pedagogical technologies, and there is no doubt that today's talented pupils and students will become great specialists in the future. It is known that the field of science and education must always be in tune with the times and meet the demands of the times. Today's education system in our country is completely different from the system 10-15 years ago. In fact, as a result

of the reforms carried out during the past period, the level of quality and efficiency of personnel training in Uzbekistan has increased significantly. However, reforms in the sector are not going well. For this, it is necessary to solve and fulfill a number of problems and tasks. In particular, education and training of young people using innovative technologies is among them. After all, the knowledge and skills, enlightenment and spirituality of our young people who are educated on the basis of advanced pedagogical and innovative technologies will be high. It is a matter for us that our young people receive education in such a spirit.

In fact, the development of the education system in all countries that have achieved high development and comfortable living standards today is also at a high level. Therefore, since the first years of independence, attention has been paid to the field of education in our country at the level of state policy. A number of laws and other normative documents related to this field, such as the Law on Education, the National Program for Personnel Training, have been adopted and are being drafted.

It should be noted that during the past period, a number of positive works have been carried out in the field of education in our Republic, and promising projects for further development of this field have been determined in the future. It should also be noted that trainings using innovative technologies are equally important and significant for both students and professors. If innovative technologies teach young people to think independently, to consolidate their knowledge and to gain deep, detailed knowledge about a specific topic, it encourages us teachers to be creative and, most importantly, to always work on ourselves. We must recognize the fact that the student of today is different from the student of yesterday. Today's students cannot be taught with yesterday's information, traditional lecture and conversation, questions and answers. In such a case, it is very likely that teaching will make students bored and lose their interest in science. After all, in today's globalization

conditions, pupils, students and young people in general are getting a lot of new information every day, being connected to various social networks on the Internet through mobile communication devices. Therefore, we, professors and teachers, must keep up with the times, conduct our lectures and seminars using innovative technologies.

It should be noted that innovative technologies can be used in all disciplines. It is natural that its appearances and forms are different depending on the content and essence of the applied science. Also, discovering new innovative technologies for each subject or lesson does not have to be overwhelming. Because so far many innovative technologies have been created. We are only required to adapt them for our subject and subjects. As an example, it is recommended to use the innovative technology in the lessons of etiquette and educational hours in the following way. This innovative technology was created on the basis of FSMU and problem-based lesson technologies. In this, students are asked the following one general question and four questions arising from it:

The problem of excessive use of mobile communications:

1. What do you know about the origin of cellular communication?
2. Give information about the positive and negative aspects of mobile communication and its excessive use.
3. What laws do you know that regulate the use of mobile communication devices?
4. Your personal proposal for regulation of excessive use of mobile communications.

As can be seen from the essence of the above innovative technology, it enables students to think independently, and most importantly, to express their opinions

freely. In it, students reflect on the importance of mobile communication tools, one of the rare discoveries of development, and the negative impact of its excessive use on our moral life. Most importantly, students will have the opportunity to make their own reasoned personal propositions about how to reduce the negative effects of excessive cell phone use on our lives. This innovative technology can be used individually or in groups according to the number of students in study groups.

The use of interactive methods and effective teaching technologies, and most importantly, an innovative approach to the professional activity of a teacher, stimulates the intellectual activity of students, contributes to the development of creative abilities in students, and helps to establish a close connection in the joint research activities of students and teachers of a department of a certain direction.

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